

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.20681233

Fintech And Operational Efficiency Of Deposit Money Banks In Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the effect of FinTech on the operational efficiency of deposit money banks in Nigeria. FinTech was proxied by mobile banking transaction value (MBTV), internet banking transaction value (IBTV), point-of-sale transaction value (POSTV), and FinTech expenditure (FTE), while operational efficiency was measured using cost-to-income ratio (CIR). The study adopted a quantitative research design based on an ex-post facto approach. Annual time-series data covering the period 2006–2025 were obtained from the Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin and the Nigeria Inter-Bank Settlement System database. The population comprised all deposit money banks operating in Nigeria, while purposive sampling was employed in selecting the study variables. Data were analyzed using ordinary least squares regression with the aid of E-Views 9.0. Preliminary analyses included descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, variance inflation factor, group unit root test, Johansen cointegration test, and model validity tests. The findings revealed that the explanatory variables jointly explained approximately 89.84 percent of the variations in CIR, while the overall regression model was statistically significant. Specifically, MBTV exerted a significant negative effect on CIR, indicating that increased mobile banking transactions enhance operational efficiency. IBTV also had a significant negative effect on CIR, suggesting that internet banking contributes positively to efficiency by reducing operating costs. Similarly, POSTV exerted a significant negative effect on CIR, implying that increased utilization of POS channels improves operational efficiency. Conversely, FTE had a significant positive effect on CIR, indicating that FinTech expenditure increases operating costs and reduces efficiency in the short run. The study concluded that digital banking channels significantly enhance the operational efficiency of Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria, whereas the immediate cost implications of FinTech investments may temporarily offset efficiency gains. The study recommended increased promotion of mobile banking, strengthening of internet banking infrastructure, expansion of POS networks, and adoption of cost-effective FinTech investment strategies to improve operational efficiency within the Nigerian banking sector.

Keywords: FinTech, mobile banking transaction value, internet banking transaction value, point-of-sale transaction value, fintech expenditure, operational efficiency and cost-to-income ratio.

INTRODUCTION

The emergence of financial technology (FinTech) has significantly transformed the banking industry by introducing digital innovations that enhance the delivery of financial services. FinTech encompasses the application of technology to banking operations, payment systems, and customer service processes, thereby improving efficiency, accessibility, and convenience. In Nigeria, the adoption of FinTech has reshaped traditional banking practices and encouraged deposit money banks (DMBs) to deploy digital platforms that support faster transactions and improved service delivery. According to Adiga et al. (2022), financial technology has become a major driver of banking sector

performance through efficient transaction processing and enhanced service provision. Similarly, Ologunwa et al. (2024) observed that the integration of FinTech into banking operations has strengthened the competitiveness of DMBs and improved their ability to meet evolving customer needs.

The increasing acceptance of digital financial services has led to substantial growth in the use of mobile banking, internet banking, and point-of-sale (POS) platforms across Nigeria. These channels enable customers to conduct transactions conveniently without visiting banking halls, thereby increasing the speed and accessibility of banking services. Chukwu and Molokwu (2022) noted that digital banking platforms have enhanced customer access to financial services and improved bank performance. Likewise, Gbanador (2023) argued that electronic banking systems have become indispensable to modern banking operations because they facilitate faster transactions and greater customer satisfaction. Consequently, mobile banking transaction value (MBTV), internet banking transaction value (IBTV), and POS transaction value (POSTV) have emerged as important indicators of FinTech adoption within the Nigerian banking sector.

The growing volume and value of transactions processed through these channels have necessitated continuous investment in technology infrastructure, software development, cybersecurity, and employee training. Such investments, commonly referred to as FinTech Expenditure (FTE), demonstrate the commitment of banks to sustaining and expanding their digital capabilities. Okey-Nwala (2025) maintained that FinTech investment is crucial for improving banking operations and supporting the increasing demand for digital financial services. Similarly, Okwor (2024) emphasized that sustained technological investment enhances the ability of banks to provide reliable, secure, and efficient services. As digital transformation continues to redefine banking operations, operational efficiency has become a major concern for DMBs. Operational efficiency, often measured by the cost-to-income ratio (CIR), reflects the ability of banks to generate income while minimizing operating costs. Ashiru et al. (2023) asserted that financial innovation influences operational outcomes by improving cost management and service delivery processes.

Despite the increasing adoption of FinTech, concerns remain regarding whether investments in mobile banking, internet banking, POS platforms, and related technologies have translated into improved operational efficiency. Although previous studies have examined the effect of FinTech on financial performance, profitability, growth, and service delivery, limited attention has been devoted to operational efficiency. For instance, Muhammad et al. (2022) focused on financial service delivery, Ashiru et al. (2023) examined financial performance, Nwankwo and Okoli (2023) investigated profitability, Ologunwa et al. (2024) assessed financial performance, while Okwor (2024) concentrated on bank growth. Consequently, empirical evidence remains limited on the extent to which MBTV, IBTV, POSTV, and FTE influence operational efficiency measured by CIR among Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria, thereby necessitating this study.

Conceptual Review

FinTech

Financial technology (FinTech) refers to the integration of innovative digital technologies into the provision of financial products and services to enhance efficiency, accessibility, speed, and convenience in financial transactions. FinTech encompasses a wide range of technological applications, including mobile banking, internet banking, electronic payment systems, digital lending platforms, artificial intelligence, and data analytics. The concept has evolved from merely supporting banking operations to becoming a strategic tool for achieving competitive advantage and operational excellence in the financial sector. According to Abdulmumin and Omotosho (2025), FinTech has fundamentally transformed the operations of DMB in Nigeria through the deployment of digital transaction channels such as mobile banking, internet banking, and Point-of-Sale (POS) systems. Similarly, Okey-Nwala (2025) argued that FinTech enhances banking performance by improving service delivery, facilitating faster transactions, and strengthening customer engagement. The increasing adoption of digital technologies has therefore positioned FinTech as a critical driver of innovation and modernization within the Nigerian banking industry.

The growing relevance of FinTech is evident in the operational activities of DMBs, where digital platforms have become central to customer service delivery and transaction processing. FinTech enables banks to reduce dependence on traditional branch operations, improve transaction efficiency,

and expand financial services to previously underserved populations. Iyobo (2025) observed that digital banking technologies significantly influence the performance of DMBs by enhancing operational processes and increasing customer accessibility. Furthermore, John (2025) found that digital and virtual banking activities positively affect the operations of Nigerian DMBs, particularly through improvements in transaction processing and service efficiency. In the same vein, Gbanador et al. (2022) maintained that financial innovation contributes significantly to the performance of DMBs by promoting technological advancement and operational improvement. Consequently, FinTech has become an indispensable component of modern banking operations in Nigeria, influencing how banks generate value, manage costs, and respond to changing customer expectations in an increasingly digital financial environment.

Operational Efficiency of DMBs in Nigeria

Operational efficiency is a critical indicator of the ability of deposit money banks to utilize available resources effectively while minimizing operating costs and maximizing income generation. In the banking sector, operational efficiency reflects how well management converts operational expenses into revenue and sustains profitability over time. One of the most widely accepted measures of operational efficiency is the cost-to-income ratio (CIR), which assesses the proportion of operating expenses relative to operating income. A lower CIR indicates greater efficiency because a smaller percentage of income is consumed by operational costs, whereas a higher CIR suggests inefficiency in resource utilization. According to Olarewaju and Msomi (2023), operational efficiency remains a key determinant of banking sector stability and competitiveness because efficient banks are better positioned to withstand economic uncertainties and maintain sustainable performance. Similarly, Ajibike and Aremu (2024) asserted that effective cost management enhances the capacity of banks to optimize income generation and improve overall operational outcomes. Consequently, operational efficiency has become an important benchmark for evaluating the performance of DMBs in an increasingly competitive financial environment.

The relevance of operational efficiency has become more pronounced in the Nigerian banking sector due to rising operational costs, technological investments, and changing customer expectations. As banks continue to modernize their operations and expand service delivery channels, attention has shifted toward the ability of these institutions to control costs while maintaining revenue growth. Okechukwu and Nwosu (2022) observed that efficient management of operating expenses is essential for sustaining the financial health of Nigerian banks and improving shareholder value. Likewise, Adeyemi and Ojo (2025) maintained that cost-to-income ratio provides a comprehensive assessment of banking efficiency because it captures both cost control and income-generating capacity. Furthermore, Eze and Nkamnebe (2024) argued that improvements in operational efficiency contribute significantly to long-term banking sustainability by enhancing productivity and resource allocation. Therefore, the Cost-to-Income Ratio remains a crucial measure for assessing the operational efficiency of DMBs in Nigeria and understanding how internal and external factors influence their performance.

Theoretical Review

The study was anchored on the technology acceptance model (TAM) and diffusion of innovation theory (DOI), which explain how the adoption and diffusion of financial technologies influence banking operations. The theories provide a basis for understanding how MBTV, IBTV, POSTV, and FTE affect the operational efficiency of DMBs in Nigeria.

Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)

The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) was propounded by Fred Davis in 1986 and later refined in 1989 to explain the factors influencing the acceptance and usage of technological innovations. The theory posits that an individual's intention to adopt a technology is primarily determined by two factors: perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use. Perceived usefulness refers to the extent to which a user believes that a technology will enhance performance, while perceived ease of use relates to the degree to which the technology is free from effort. In the banking industry, TAM explains the adoption of FinTech channels such as mobile banking, internet banking, and POS platforms by customers and financial institutions. The theory is relevant to this study because increased acceptance and utilization of these digital channels can improve transaction efficiency, reduce operational bottlenecks, and ultimately influence the cost-to-income ratio of DMBs in Nigeria.

Diffusion of Innovation Theory (DOI)

The Diffusion of Innovation Theory was propounded by Everett Rogers in 1962 to explain how innovations are communicated, adopted, and spread within a social system over time. The theory identifies innovation characteristics such as relative advantage, compatibility, complexity, trialability, and observability as determinants of adoption. According to the theory, innovations that offer superior benefits compared to existing methods are more likely to be adopted rapidly. In the banking sector, FinTech innovations such as mobile banking, internet banking, and POS technologies diffuse among banks and customers based on their perceived advantages and effectiveness. The theory is applicable to this study because the adoption and diffusion of FinTech services among deposit money banks can enhance service delivery, improve operational processes, reduce transaction costs, and contribute to operational efficiency as measured by the cost-to-income ratio.

Empirical Review

Oluwapelumi and Isibor (2026) examined the effect of FinTech adoption on the operational performance of Nigerian DMBs. Secondary data obtained from commercial banks, the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), and Nigeria Inter-Bank Settlement System (NIBSS) were analyzed using multiple regression techniques. Findings revealed that FinTech significantly improved operational efficiency by reducing transaction costs and enhancing service delivery speed. The study concluded that FinTech is a strategic tool for improving banking performance and recommended increased FinTech expenditure, workforce digital training, and supportive regulatory policies.

Abdulmumin and Omotosho (2025) investigated the effect of FinTech adoption on the performance of DMBs in Nigeria between 2014 and 2023. Using quarterly data from CBN, NIBSS, and NDIC, the study adopted an ex-post facto design and ARDL estimation technique. Findings showed that POS and mobile banking transactions significantly enhanced bank performance, while internet banking produced mixed results. The study concluded that FinTech is an important driver of banking efficiency and recommended sustained investment in digital infrastructure and customer-focused technological innovations.

Agaba (2025) examined the impact of financial technology on the performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria using quarterly data from 2012Q1 to 2023Q4. Data were sourced from CBN, NIBSS, and NDIC and analyzed using the ARDL model. The findings indicated that increasing volumes of mobile banking, internet banking, and POS transactions significantly improved operational efficiency and reduced transaction costs. The study concluded that FinTech positively influences banking productivity and recommended stronger regulatory support and investment in digital banking infrastructure.

Vincent (2025) investigated the impact of digital payment platforms on the financial performance of Nigerian deposit money banks from 2009 to 2023. The study used secondary data obtained from annual reports, CBN Statistical Bulletins, and NIBSS reports. Employing panel regression analysis, the findings revealed that POS and mobile payment transactions significantly enhanced performance by reducing operational costs and increasing efficiency. The study concluded that digital payment channels improve banking operations and recommended continuous expansion of digital financial services across the banking industry.

Okey-Nwala (2025) assessed the effect of financial technology on commercial bank performance in Nigeria using Return on Assets as a performance indicator. Covering the period 2010–2023, the study utilized secondary data from CBN and NIBSS publications and analyzed them using multiple regression techniques. Findings revealed that mobile banking and POS transaction values positively affected bank performance, while internet banking showed a weaker positive impact. The study concluded that FinTech improves banking efficiency and profitability and recommended increased FinTech expenditure to enhance service delivery.

Ally (2025) investigated the role of FinTech in enhancing bank efficiency among commercial banks in Tanzania. Using panel data from commercial banks and applying the two-step Generalized Method of Moments (GMM) technique, the study found a strong positive relationship between FinTech adoption and operational efficiency. The findings showed that FinTech significantly reduced costs and improved productivity, particularly among larger banks. The study concluded that digital innovation enhances banking performance and recommended accelerated digital transformation initiatives across the banking sector.

Yang et al. (2025) examined the effect of FinTech on the financial sustainability of Chinese commercial banks. The study covered 104 banks between 2015 and 2023 using a three-stage Network DEA-Malmquist model and a two-way fixed-effects approach. Findings indicated that while FinTech encouraged innovation, excessive competition from FinTech firms negatively affected loan efficiency and profitability. The study concluded that banks should balance technological expansion with effective risk management and recommended strengthening internal innovation capabilities to sustain long-term performance.

Halilu (2024) examined the impact of digital banking adoption on the financial performance of listed DMBs in Nigeria from 2013 to 2022. Using secondary data from annual reports and CBN publications, the study employed panel regression analysis under an ex-post facto research design. Findings revealed that mobile and internet banking significantly improved operational outcomes by reducing service costs and enhancing customer accessibility. The study concluded that digital banking strengthens operational efficiency and recommended increased investment in digital banking technologies and infrastructure.

Awendo and Mwanzia (2022) investigated the effect of alternative banking channels on the financial performance of commercial banks in Kenya. The study focused on mobile banking, internet banking, and POS services using panel data from commercial bank reports and central bank publications. Multiple regression analysis revealed that mobile and internet banking significantly improved bank efficiency through reduced transaction costs and increased accessibility. The study concluded that alternative banking channels promote operational efficiency and recommended further investment in digital banking infrastructure to enhance financial performance.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a quantitative research design based on an *ex-post facto* approach, given that the variables of interest were historical in nature and not subject to manipulation by the researcher. This design facilitated the examination of the effect of financial technology (FinTech) on the operational efficiency of deposit money banks (DMBs) in Nigeria over time. The study utilized a time-series framework to capture annual variations in FinTech indicators and operational efficiency from 2006 to 2025. The population of the study comprised all Deposit Money Banks operating in Nigeria, which constitute the primary institutions responsible for the provision of digital financial services within the banking sector. However, the study adopted a purposive sampling technique by selecting specific variables that adequately represent the constructs under investigation. FinTech was proxied by mobile banking transaction value (MBTV), internet banking transaction value (IBTV), point-of-sale transaction value (POSTV), and fintech expenditure (FTE), while operational efficiency was proxied by cost-to-income ratio (CIR). Secondary data were sourced from the CBN Statistical Bulletin and the NIBSS database for the period 2006–2025.

Data analysis was conducted using the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression technique with the aid of E-Views 9.0 software. Descriptive statistics were first employed to summarize the distributional characteristics of the variables through measures such as mean, maximum value, minimum value, standard deviation, skewness, and kurtosis. Correlation analysis was conducted to examine the degree and direction of association among the variables, while Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) analysis was used to detect multicollinearity among the explanatory variables. The decision rule for VIF was that values below 10 indicate the absence of multicollinearity, whereas values above 10 suggest multicollinearity. The Group Unit Root Test was conducted to determine the stationarity properties of the variables, with the null hypothesis of non-stationarity rejected when the probability value was less than 0.05. The Johansen Cointegration Test was employed to examine the existence of long-run relationships among the variables. The null hypothesis of no cointegration was rejected when the Trace Statistic or Maximum Eigenvalue Statistic exceeded the corresponding critical values at the 5 percent significance level. Model validity was assessed using the coefficient of determination (R^2), Adjusted R^2 , F-statistic, and Durbin-Watson statistic. The model was considered statistically significant when the probability value of the F-statistic was less than 0.05, while a Durbin-Watson value close to 2 indicated the absence of autocorrelation.

The OLS regression model was specified as:

$$CIR_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 MBTV_t + \beta_2 IBTV_t + \beta_3 POSTV_t + \beta_4 FTE_t + \mu_t$$

Where CIR represents Cost-to-Income Ratio, MBTV denotes Mobile Banking Transaction Value, IBTV represents Internet Banking Transaction Value, POSTV captures Point-of-Sale Transaction Value, and FTE measures FinTech Expenditure. β_0 is the intercept, β_1 – β_4 are the slope coefficients, and μ_t is the stochastic error term. Each variable was measured using annual data obtained from the selected sources to ensure consistency, reliability, and empirical validity.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Assessing the influence of financial technology on the operational efficiency of DMBs is crucial for understanding the effectiveness of digital banking innovations in Nigeria. This study investigated the effects of MBTV, IBTV, POSTV, and FTE on CIR from 2006 to 2025. OLS regression was employed, while descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, variance inflation factor, model validity, unit root and cointegration tests were conducted to ensure the reliability and robustness of the empirical results.

Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive statistics were employed to summarize the distributional characteristics of MBTV, IBTV, POSTV, FTE, and CIR through measures such as mean, maximum, minimum, standard deviation, skewness, and kurtosis. (See Table 1 below).

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

	CIR	MBTV	IBTV	POSTV	FTE
Mean	61.35200	2007.158	1821.604	2089.207	58.65100
Median	61.30000	705.6550	931.5250	495.8650	38.67500
Maximum	68.00000	9769.550	7148.140	11952.61	185.7200
Minimum	54.80000	50.00000	120.0000	20.00000	8.000000
Std. Dev.	5.229915	2747.523	2048.734	3279.814	53.02740
Skewness	0.012537	1.625517	1.327460	1.872348	1.061415
Kurtosis	1.368420	4.646788	3.699085	5.571026	3.012558
Jarque-Bera	2.218902	1.706761	4.281098	1.719410	3.755472
Probability	0.329740	0.423951	0.083259	0.421835	0.152936
Sum	1227.040	40143.15	36432.08	41784.13	1173.020
Sum Sq. Dev.	519.6881	14342880	79748892	20438640	53426.20
Observations	20	20	20	20	20

Source: E-VIEW 9.0 (2026).

The descriptive statistics revealed that CIR averaged 61.35%, indicating that operating expenses constituted a substantial proportion of operating income during the study period. MBTV, IBTV, and POSTV recorded mean values of 2007.16, 1821.60, and 2089.21 respectively, reflecting increased adoption of digital banking channels, while FTE averaged 58.65. The positive skewness values indicate right-skewed distributions across all variables. Furthermore, the Jarque-Bera probability values exceeded 0.05 for all variables, suggesting normality and supporting the suitability of the data for subsequent econometric analyses.

Correlation Analysis

Correlation analysis was conducted to determine the degree and direction of association among MBTV, IBTV, POSTV, FTE, and CIR, and to provide preliminary evidence of their relationships. (See Table 2 below).

Table 2: Correlation Matrix for the Independent and Dependent Variables

	CIR	MBTV	IBTV	POSTV	FTE
CIR	1.000000				
MBTV	-0.781470	1.000000			
IBTV	-0.640584	0.694521	1.000000		
POSTV	-0.729996	0.696435	0.582277	1.000000	
FTE	-0.787700	0.780115	0.695424	0.760370	1.000000

Source: E-VIEW 9.0 (2026).

The correlation results showed that MBTV (-0.7815), IBTV (-0.6406), POSTV (-0.7300), and FTE (-0.7877) each exhibited a strong negative relationship with CIR. This implies that increases in digital transaction values and FinTech investment are associated with reductions in the cost-to-income ratio, thereby enhancing operational efficiency. Furthermore, the positive correlations among the

explanatory variables ranged from 0.5823 to 0.7801, indicating moderate associations. Since none of the correlation coefficients exceeded 0.80, there is no indication of serious multicollinearity among the independent variables.

Variance Inflation Factors

Variance Inflation Factors were utilized to assess the presence of multicollinearity among MBTV, IBTV, POSTV, and FTE, ensuring that the explanatory variables were sufficiently independent for reliable estimation. (See Table 3 below).

Table 3: Variance Inflation Factors Multicollinearity Test

Variance Inflation Factors

Date: 06/03/26 Time: 12:43

Sample: 2006 2025

Included observations: 20

Variable	Coefficient Variance	Uncentered VIF	Centered VIF
MBTV	2.012365	44.48599	3.275384
IBTV	1.162601	15.54267	1.483193
POSTV	1.627121	19.90950	1.695091
FTE	2.116209	25.15037	2.099357
C	1.551289	19.52332	NA

Source: E-VIEW 9.0 (2026).

The Variance Inflation Factor results indicated that MBTV, IBTV, POSTV, and FTE recorded centered VIF values of 3.2754, 1.4832, 1.6951, and 2.0994 respectively. Since all centered VIF values are below the threshold of 10, there is no evidence of serious multicollinearity among the explanatory variables. This suggests that each variable contributes distinct information to the model and that the estimated coefficients are reliable. Consequently, MBTV, IBTV, POSTV, and FTE can be jointly included in the regression model without compromising the validity of the estimated results.

Model Validity Tests

Model validity tests were performed to evaluate the goodness-of-fit and overall significance of the model using R², Adjusted R², F-statistic, and Durbin-Watson statistic. (See Table 4 below).

Table 4: Model Validity Test

Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test:

F-statistic	6.654410	Prob. F(2,13)	0.1283
Obs*R-squared	4.385522	Prob. Chi-Square(2)	0.1028
		Durbin-Watson stat	2.018021

Heteroskedasticity Test: Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey

F-statistic	0.301932	Prob. F(4,15)	0.8721
Obs*R-squared	1.490310	Prob. Chi-Square(4)	0.8284
Scaled explained SS	0.242384	Prob. Chi-Square(4)	0.9932
		Durbin-Watson stat	1.883855

Ramsey RESET Test

Equation: UNTITLED

Specification: CIR MBTV IBTV POSTV FTE C

Omitted Variables: Squares of fitted values

	Value	Df	Probability	Value
t-statistic	2.971059	14	0.1918	2.971059
F-statistic	2.887193	(1, 14)	0.1926	2.887193
Likelihood ratio	3.819371	1	0.2112	3.819371

Durbin-Watson stat 1.767437

Source: E-VIEW 9.0 (2026).

The diagnostic test results confirmed the suitability of the model for analysis. The Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test produced probability values of 0.1283 and 0.1028, both exceeding 0.05, indicating the absence of serial correlation. The Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey Heteroskedasticity Test recorded probability values of 0.8721, 0.8284, and 0.9932, suggesting homoskedastic residuals and

constant error variance. Furthermore, the Ramsey RESET Test yielded probability values above 0.05, indicating no specification error and confirming the correctness of the model's functional form. The Durbin-Watson statistics, being close to 2, further support the absence of autocorrelation.

Group Unit Root Test

The Group Unit Root Test was conducted to determine the stationarity properties of MBTV, IBTV, POSTV, FTE, and CIR, thereby preventing the estimation of spurious regression results. (See Table 5 below).

Table 5: Group Unit Root Test

Group unit root test: Summary
 Series: CIR, MBTV, IBTV, POSTV, FTE
 Date: 06/03/26 Time: 12:51
 Sample: 2006 2025
 Exogenous variables: Individual effects
 Automatic selection of maximum lags
 Automatic lag length selection based on SIC: 4
 Newey-West automatic bandwidth selection and Bartlett kernel
 Balanced observations for each test

Method	Statistic	Prob.**	Cross-sections	Obs
Null: Unit root (assumes common unit root process)				
Levin, Lin & Chu t*	2.29202	0.9890	1	15
Null: Unit root (assumes individual unit root process)				
Im, Pesaran and Shin W-stat	1.36822	0.9144	1	15
ADF - Fisher Chi-square	0.06342	0.9688	1	15
PP - Fisher Chi-square	0.22628	0.8930	1	19

** Probabilities for Fisher tests are computed using an asymptotic Chi-square distribution. All other tests assume asymptotic normality.

Group unit root test: Summary
 Series: CIR, MBTV, IBTV, POSTV, FTE
 Date: 06/03/26 Time: 12:51
 Sample: 2006 2025
 Exogenous variables: Individual effects
 Automatic selection of maximum lags
 Automatic lag length selection based on SIC: 3
 Newey-West automatic bandwidth selection and Bartlett kernel
 Balanced observations for each test

Method	Statistic	Prob.**	Cross-sections	Obs
Null: Unit root (assumes common unit root process)				
Levin, Lin & Chu t*	19.9674	0.0000	2	30
Null: Unit root (assumes individual unit root process)				
Im, Pesaran and Shin W-stat	11.9746	0.0118	2	30
ADF - Fisher Chi-square	13.3951	0.0095	2	30
PP - Fisher Chi-square	14.0654	0.0072	2	36

** Probabilities for Fisher tests are computed using an asymptotic Chi-square distribution. All other tests assume asymptotic normality.

Source: E-VIEW 9.0 (2026).

The group unit root test results indicated that all variables were non-stationary at level, as the probability values of the Levin, Lin and Chu, Im, Pesaran and Shin, ADF-Fisher, and PP-Fisher tests exceeded 0.05. However, after first differencing, the probability values for all tests became less than 0.05, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis of unit root. This implies that CIR, MBTV, IBTV,

POSTV, and FTE attained stationarity at first difference, indicating that the variables are integrated of order one, I(1), and suitable for cointegration analysis.

Johansen Cointegration Test

The Johansen Cointegration Test was employed to ascertain whether a long-run equilibrium relationship exists among MBTV, IBTV, POSTV, FTE, and CIR over the study period. (See Table 6 below).

Table 6: Johansen Cointegration Test

Date: 06/03/26 Time: 12:54
 Sample (adjusted): 2008 2025
 Included observations: 18 after adjustments
 Trend assumption: Linear deterministic trend
 Series: CIR MBTV IBTV POSTV FTE
 Lags interval (in first differences): 1 to 1

Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Trace)

Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Trace Statistic	0.05 Critical Value	Prob.**
None *	0.998354	203.0777	69.81889	0.0000
At most 1 *	0.884131	87.71043	47.85613	0.0000
At most 2 *	0.758561	48.91507	29.79707	0.0001
At most 3 *	0.657189	23.33457	15.49471	0.0027
At most 4 *	0.202115	4.064227	3.841466	0.0438

Trace test indicates 5 cointegrating eqn(s) at the 0.05 level

* denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level

**MacKinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) p-values

Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Maximum Eigenvalue)

Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Max-Eigen Statistic	0.05 Critical Value	Prob.**
None *	0.998354	115.3673	33.87687	0.0000
At most 1 *	0.884131	38.79536	27.58434	0.0012
At most 2 *	0.758561	25.58050	21.13162	0.0110
At most 3 *	0.657189	19.27034	14.26460	0.0074
At most 4 *	0.202115	4.064227	3.841466	0.0438

Source: E-VIEW 9.0 (2026).

The Johansen Cointegration Test results revealed the existence of a long-run equilibrium relationship among CIR, MBTV, IBTV, POSTV, and FTE. Both the Trace Test and Maximum Eigenvalue Test indicate the rejection of the null hypotheses at the 5% significance level, as the test statistics exceeded their corresponding critical values and the probability values were less than 0.05. Specifically, the Trace Test identified five cointegrating equations, while the Maximum Eigenvalue Test confirmed the same result. This suggests that the variables move together in the long run and that a stable relationship exists among them despite short-run fluctuations.

OLS Regression Analysis

OLS Regression Analysis was applied to estimate the effect of MBTV, IBTV, POSTV, and FTE on CIR and determine the significance and direction of their relationships. (See Table 7 below).

Table 7: Regression Result

Dependent Variable: CIR
 Method: Least Squares
 Date: 06/03/26 Time: 12:32
 Sample: 2006 2025
 Included observations: 20

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
MBTV	-0.144497	0.019111	-7.561057	0.0000
IBTV	-0.167130	0.024510	-6.818808	0.0000
POSTV	-0.048088	0.006209	-7.745182	0.0000
FTE	1.858465	0.340895	5.451730	0.0001
C	67.23290	0.742489	90.55076	0.0000
R-squared	0.898370	Mean dependent var		61.35200
Adjusted R-squared	0.897935	S.D. dependent var		5.229915
S.E. of regression	0.237645	Akaike info criterion		0.176237
Sum squared resid	0.847124	Schwarz criterion		0.425170
Log likelihood	3.237632	Hannan-Quinn criter.		0.224831
F-statistic	2296.775	Durbin-Watson stat		1.772249
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

Source: E-VIEW 9.0 (2026).

The OLS regression results indicated that the explanatory variables jointly explain approximately 89.84% of the variations in CIR, as evidenced by the R-squared value of 0.898370. The Adjusted R-squared value of 0.897935 further confirms the strong explanatory power of the model after adjusting for the number of predictors. The F-statistic of 2296.775 with a probability value of 0.0000 indicates that the overall model is statistically significant. Furthermore, the Durbin-Watson statistic of 1.772249 suggests the absence of serious autocorrelation in the residuals, implying that the estimated model is reliable for inference.

The finding revealed that MBTV has a significant negative effect on CIR, implying that increased mobile banking transactions improve the operational efficiency of DMBs in Nigeria. This supports TAM, which suggests that useful and easy-to-use technologies enhance performance through greater adoption. It also aligns with DOI, which posits that innovations with clear advantages are rapidly diffused. Increased mobile banking usage reduces branch-related costs and improves transaction efficiency. The finding corroborates Abdulmumin and Omotosho (2025), Agaba (2025), Vincent (2025), Halilu (2024), and Awendo and Mwanzia (2022), who found that mobile banking significantly enhances banking efficiency and operational performance.

The result showed that IBTV exerts a significant negative effect on CIR, indicating that internet banking improves the operational efficiency of DMBs. The finding is consistent with TAM, which emphasizes that technology adoption enhances organizational performance when users perceive it as beneficial. It also supports DOI, which explains that innovations with observable benefits experience wider acceptance. Through reduced physical transactions and faster service delivery, internet banking lowers operating costs and improves efficiency. The finding agrees with Agaba (2025), Halilu (2024), and Awendo and Mwanzia (2022), who reported that internet banking positively influences banking performance and operational effectiveness.

The finding that POSTV has a significant negative effect on CIR indicates that increased POS transactions enhance operational efficiency among DMBs. This outcome supports TAM because POS technology is widely accepted due to its convenience and effectiveness in facilitating payments. It also aligns with DOI, which emphasizes the diffusion of innovations that provide superior benefits. Increased POS usage contributes to higher transaction volumes and improved service delivery while reducing processing costs. The finding is consistent with Abdulmumin and Omotosho (2025), Agaba (2025), Vincent (2025), and Okey-Nwala (2025), who reported that POS transactions positively influence banking performance and efficiency.

The study found that FTE has a significant positive effect on CIR, suggesting that increased FinTech expenditure raises operating costs and reduces operational efficiency in the short run. Although TAM and DOI generally predict positive outcomes from technology adoption, the result indicates that the costs associated with technology acquisition, maintenance, cybersecurity, and staff training may initially outweigh immediate benefits. Consequently, FinTech investments may increase operating expenses before efficiency gains are realized. This finding contrasts with Oluwapelumi and Isibor (2026), Okey-Nwala (2025), Ally (2025), and Agaba (2025), who found that FinTech investments improve banking efficiency and performance.

CONCLUSION

This study examined the effect of FinTech on the operational efficiency of deposit money banks in Nigeria using MBTV, IBTV, POSTV, and FTE as proxies for FinTech and CIR as a measure of operational efficiency. The findings revealed that MBTV, IBTV, and POSTV significantly reduced CIR, indicating that increased utilization of digital banking channels enhances operational efficiency. Conversely, FTE exerted a significant positive effect on CIR, suggesting that FinTech investments increase operational costs in the short run. Overall, the study concludes that the adoption and utilization of digital banking channels contribute significantly to improving the operational efficiency of DMBs in Nigeria, although the benefits of FinTech expenditure may require a longer period to materialize fully.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- i. Based on the significant negative effect of MBTV on CIR, deposit money banks should intensify efforts to promote mobile banking adoption through improved application functionality, customer awareness, and enhanced digital security.
- ii. Given the significant negative effect of IBTV on CIR, banks should strengthen internet banking infrastructure to improve accessibility, reliability, and transaction speed.
- iii. Since POSTV significantly improved operational efficiency, banks should expand POS networks and encourage merchants and customers to increase the use of cashless payment channels.
- iv. Furthermore, owing to the significant positive effect of FTE on CIR, banks should adopt cost-effective FinTech investment strategies, prioritize projects with high efficiency potential, and ensure proper evaluation of technological investments to minimize implementation costs and accelerate the realization of operational benefits.

REFERENCES

- Abdulmumin, B. A., & Omotosho, J. O. (2025). Financial technology and the performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria. *Economic Forum*, 15(4), 48–57.
- Adeyemi, T. A., & Ojo, O. A. (2025). Cost management and operational efficiency of deposit money banks in Nigeria. *African Journal of Accounting and Financial Research*, 8(1), 44–58.
- Adiga, E. A., Adigwe, P. K., Okonkwo, O. N., & Ogbonna, K. S. (2022). Financial technology and banking sector performance in Nigeria. *International Journal of Innovative Finance and Economics Research*, 10(4), 1–12.
- Agaba, A. W. (2025). The effect of financial technology on the performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria: An autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) approach. *African Development Finance Journal*, 11(2), 87–104.
- Ajibike, J. O., & Aremu, M. A. (2024). Operational efficiency and financial sustainability of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. *International Journal of Economics and Financial Management*, 9(2), 75–89.
- Ally, O. J. (2025). Bank efficiency in the digital age: The role of financial technology. *Management and Finance Journal*, 7(1), 55–72.
- Ashiru, O., Balogun, G., & Paseda, O. (2023). Financial innovation and bank financial performance: Evidence from Nigerian deposit money banks. *Journal of Accounting and Financial Management*, 9(3), 45–59.

- Awendo, N. O., & Mwanzia, S. M. (2022). Effect of alternative banking channels on financial performance of commercial banks in Kenya. *African Journal of Finance and Management*, 14(2), 77–93.
- Chukwu, K. O., & Molokwu, S. R. (2022). Effects of digital banking on the performance of commercial banks in Nigeria, 2010–2019. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Analysis*, 5(1), 133–148.
- Davis, F. D. (1989). Perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, and user acceptance of information technology. *MIS Quarterly*, 13(3), 319–340.
- Eze, C. U., & Nkamnebe, A. D. (2024). Banking efficiency and performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Management Sciences*, 25(1), 112–126.
- Gbanador, M. A. (2023). Electronic banking systems and the performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Management Sciences*, 24(1A), 360–371.
- Gbanador, M. A., Makwe, E. U., & Olushola, O. A. (2022). Financial innovation and the performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria. *IIARD International Journal of Banking and Finance Research*, 2, 37–50.
- Halilu, A. (2024). Digital banking adoption and financial performance of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. *International Journal of Accounting Research and Management Sciences*, 9(1), 34–49.
- Iyobo, E. B. (2025). Digital banking and the performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria. *African Journal of Business Development and Management Research*, 10(1), 45–61.
- John, J. I. (2025). Digital and virtual banking on the operations of Nigerian deposit money banks. *Covenant Journal of Business and Applied Finance*, 4(2), 32–41.
- Muhammad, S. N. I., Abdulmalik, A. Y., & Halima, S. (2022). The impact of financial technology (FinTech) on financial service delivery of deposit money banks in Nigeria. *Sapientia Foundation Journal of Education, Sciences and Gender Studies*, 4(2), 83–93.
- Nwankwo, B. C., & Okoli, O. C. (2023). Effect of financial technology on the profitability of deposit money banks in Nigeria. *UBS Journal of Business and Economic Policy*, 1(2), 52–71.
- Okechukwu, P. N., & Nwosu, B. E. (2022). Operating cost management and financial performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria. *Journal of Accounting and Financial Management*, 8(4), 21–35.
- Okey-Nwala, P. O. (2025). Financial technology and banking sector performance in Nigeria. *IRASS Journal of Economics and Business Management*, 2(3), 8–14.
- Okwor, E. E. (2024). Impact of financial technology on the growth of deposit money banks in Nigeria. *Seybold Report Journal*, 19(5), 154–170.
- Olarewaju, O. M., & Msomi, T. S. (2023). Operational efficiency and bank performance in emerging economies: Evidence from the banking sector. *Banks and Bank Systems*, 18(3), 135–146.
- Ologunwa, O. P., Yusuf, R. A., & Obamuyi, T. M. (2024). Effect of financial technology on financial performance of deposit money banks in Southwest Nigeria. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science*, 8(2), 1974–1986.
- Oluwapelumi, I., & Isibor, A. A. (2026). Financial technology adoption and deposit money bank operational performance in Nigeria. *Journal of Accounting and Financial Management*, 12(3), 397–410.
- Rogers, E. M. (1962). *Diffusion of innovations*. Free Press.
- Rogers, E. M. (2003). *Diffusion of innovations* (5th ed.). Free Press.
- Vincent, A. O., Isibor, A., & Akinrinola, O. (2025). Digital payment platforms and financial performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria. *African Journal of Accounting and Financial Research*, 8(3), 167–181.
- Yang, Y., Yang, F., Yi, X., & He, D. (2025). How FinTech affects financial sustainability: Evidence from Chinese commercial banks using a three-stage network DEA-Malmquist model. *Finance Research Letters*, 74, 107214.